

SOURCE WITH AT WORK SUGGESTIONS

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarixiy manbalarni o'rganish masalasi va hozirgi kun o'quvchilariga o'rgatish usullari, aniq ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. XV-XIX asrga tegishli adabiy manbalar sanab o'tilgan.

Abstract: This article presents specific information on the issue of studying historical sources and methods of teaching them to today's students. Literary sources of the XV-XIX centuries are listed.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена конкретная информация по вопросу изучения исторических источников и методам их преподавания современным студентам. Перечислены литературные источники XV-XIX веков.

Kalit so'zlar: Munaqqid, shams, guruh, firqa, sulola, mahzab, sivilizatsiya, xiroj.

Key words: Munaqqid, shams, group, faction, dynasty, sect, civilization, khiroj.

Ключевые слова: Мунаккид, шамс, группа, фракция, династия, секта, цивилизация, хиродж.

Humanity centuries during created historical , scientific , literary culture I agree until now preserved is coming . Adamzod by created legacy the future to the whole generation arrived to go , their value own still storage for all equal to is responsible . The reason the past written oral samples the future to generation deliver textual studies and source studies of science current of duties is one East wake up of the era the great ones growing XV century second half of the 16th century heads Uzbek literature history richest resources created Jami " Bahoristan " , Navoi works , Babur " Baburnoma " , " Khondamir " Makorim ul- ahlaq " , Koshifi " Futuvatnomai " " Sultani " Yakub youth of the 15th century the most manuscript from sources is counted . It's past century our scholars basically from manuscripts wide used Manuscript - Secretaries by book done Arabic in the alphabet moved unique tazkira , bayoz , are complexes .

Tazkira - O' in the past special written ie in itself many historical persons they are with connection issues attraction did manuscript .

Example : Abu Mansur al- Saalibi's " Orphanage " . ut-dahr " work Persian-Tajik in the language the first tazkira is considered

Turkish in the language and Alisher Navoi's work " Majolis un- nafaos " . first of all tazkira is considered

This is the point " Baburnoma " is also a memoir work as to the language if we get not updated we will be

XV century literary sources one to the place sum up them textual studies source studies point of view in terms of study today's modern education with approach in comparison analysis to do of textual studies is the task .

Critical analysis being done of the work achievement and disadvantages to show in order to him another to works compares " good " and " bad " aspects shows ¹.

The narrative of historical facts and events gives information about the character of a person . it can be interpreted differently in the interests of groups, sects, dynasties, sects and countries.

The work or scientific source being read is one of the important areas of history science, which serves to get impartial and objective knowledge about the history of our country, to understand our identity, and to know our rich and ancient culture.

Historical sources can be divided into the following six main groups depending on their general character and reflection of the past.

1. *Written sources* ; 2. *Material resources* ; 3. *Ethnographic sources* ; 4. *Linguistic sources* ; 5. *People sweet tooth literature* ; 6. *A miracle picture-miniatures* .

Written sources historical of sources important and main is the type . Navoi's work " *Khamsa* " . take let's write in 1483-1485 finished work as we know This is a work five huge from epics consists of education and morality own into incarnate gave Babur in " *Baburnoma* " . and 1494-1529 Farg'ana , Kabul , India regions socio-political circumstances , nature events , animals and plant the world very accuracy with cause passed .

God Almighty grace with and Lord of the Universe intercession with and chahoriori of the bosafs effort with tuesday day , Ramadan of the month in five , history eight face it's enough at nine Ferghana in the region ten two young the king I ²was In this Babur's AD in account Tuesday , June 10, 1494 day to the throne that he sat down about sure information is brought . This is the place holy of our religion the most beautiful and high manners kingdom way with three dots expression will be done . 1. Kingdom fate reached To the breed thank you 2. Of the king In the ways of Rasulullah (peace be upon him). that it is is a hint . 3. Chahor burn successors that it is is a hint . (*Chahor yor : Hazrat Abu Bakr Siddiq , Hazrat Umarul-Farooq , His Holiness Usman Zinnurayn , Hazrat Ali al- Murtaza (may Allah be pleased with him anhum) efforts*) ³. Historical works sure information relies on and present young to generation that's it way arrived goes.

Written sources own _ in turn two to the group divided into :

1. Higher and local rulers from the court came out official documents (labels , decrees , grace notes , financial report notebooks , official correspondence). Such 34 types of documents specialists those who identified

2. Narrative (Latin . Narratio-story , story) written sources . Such From the sources we are historical, geographical and cosmographical, biographical, hagiographical , memoir works , tourist and ambassadors memories see we go out

The majority written works in prose creativity done _ Some historical works , including Abdulkasim Firdausi 's *Shahnama* , Muhammad Salih 's *Shaybaniinama* poetic in the direction written.

Socio- political , especially economic to relationships about issues in learning official document , financial report book and correspondence importance *benhoya* is big . Official documents socio-political life known we walked in the form directly and many p cases exactly note reach with is valuable . But their between , especially official in correspondence there

¹ Abdug Afur Rasulov . Criticism , Interpretation , Evaluation . Science, T: 2006; Page 11 .

²Babur. " Baburnoma " Zilal spring _ T: 2021; Page 24.

³ That's it source .

are also fake ones stands . That's why for also from them when used attention and caution is required . Documents on the work take when he goes , from him any socio-political event or the fact interpretation reach for use in the process , one with not satisfied , similar one how many document , sources adding to learn necessary.

Second group works about that's it to say they should dominant of the class assignment with written and that's it because of their on the pages more kings and khans, emirs life and activity illuminated , material wealth creator hard worker of the people history while a lot cases aside passed .

It is known that personality society history about 40 thousand yearly period own into takes , but writing appear to be while relatively a lot time by the way no .

For example , from the beginnings of civilization one to be Central in Asia initial writing Aramaic letter basically approx from our era previous a thousand of the year in the middle appear was. Letter historian Free Okhunjonov's information according to our country Arabic to the invasion until ten eight writing type there is was. But, unfortunately, it is old our history in itself reflection made written of monuments big part our to our time arrived did not come Theirs most of them invasion wars in time , moreover natural disasters due to no being gone.

Linguistic sources in our language , more precisely i his lexical-word wealth contained long from the past the rest, socio - economic, administrative and we walked to terms it is said . For example , rent is medium in centuries from the population, mainly from the peasants removable main tax zakat-cattle and from property the poor for per year one times removable tax Suyurgol - princes and to the emirs the crown is the throne in front showed big services for to be given land-water ; rare , attention owner item , fabric ; kings , khans and authoritative to people to be done tight ; cherik - troop ; guard - of the army took and on the sides going special military division ; caliph - Prophet Muhammad deputy , medium in centuries Arabic Muslim feudal of the state chief ; mirishkor - more precisely - miri hunting , king and of the Khans hunting birds and hunting animals imagination doer official ; Myrrh is water distribution with engaged in official ; judge - sharia based on the work driver judge label' - medium in centuries the ruler by to be given official document ; endowment - mosque, madrasa, house and to the graves a gift done land - water about Created special document and another terms very a lot occurs . This and similar terms, of course valuable historical material of our ancestors socio-political his life to learn help will give. Theirs come output and etymology linguistics learns science (Latin . Lingua - til) .

The mouth is sweet literature of culture the most ancient part being his root primitive the team and early feudalism to the system go is worn The mouth is sweet of literature some samples ancient Greek historians , as well as Tabari , Mas'udi , Beruni , Firdawsi , Ibn al- Asir such as East of scientists works through until us arrived came Kayumars , Jamshid and Siovush about legends , To' maris and Shirak about stories these are including.

Seed production period history , especially patriarchy _ relationships such as " Alpomish " , " Gorogli " in learning epics , as well as folk fairy tales , ceremony songs , matal and of riddles the role is also insignificant is big . This is the people masterpieces different social to class belongs to of people stay - life , spiritual appearance , tradition , especially long in the past judgment drove social relationships about valuable information will give .

X-XIX centuries during manuscript books to decorate for created elegant a miracle the pictures are also historical source being service does. Our country history and material items , crafts , clothes , souvenirs monuments and in general material our culture features wants to

learn if we are , elegant a miracle descriptive art samples-miniature pictures valuable source role passes. Because they have historical items image exactly, sometimes artistic creativity features customized without reflection will be delivered .

For example, great the artist master Kamaluddin Behzod's " Samarkand Grandmother of the mosque " construction ". Famous picture reminder enough. This painting is from the 15th century work weapons , construction process , then participation doing masters about perfect imagination is given Such from pictures history in learning descriptive tool as fruitful use can We are the last published in in sources of them just indifferent their use let's see can.

In general , up to us arrived came ancient mural pictures and manuscript to books processed and separately in complex ones of pictures historical source as importance very big.

See as we know, source science science research sources very a lot and different We are the most the main ones about information we gave Print again, stone print books , timely press magazine and newspapers are also historical source is considered These days technique development relationship with again sound source, photo source, Cinema - television sources and internet materials also appeared they are traditional sources denial maybe not addition tool being service to do can.

Literary sources in our learning above counting passed source of types our use , source studies , history , ethnography , visual art that's it such as many sciences with together teaching efficient the result to give no doubt.

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